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AHRĀRĪ FAMILY AFTER KHWĀJA AHRĀR (d. 896/1490): COMPETITION FOR SPIRITUAL LEADERSHIP AND WAQF ENDOWMENTS

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Abstract

The Şiddīqīs were one of the most influential strata of the holy families in the region as descendants of Abū Bakr Şiddīq. In turn, the Şiddīqīs can be divided into different local sidelines as Ḥāfīzī, Marginānī, Kūyī-‘Arifānī, Ḥakīm-Atāyī, Sharaf-Atāyī, and Ahrārī, which their appearance is associated with the names of famous Islamic scholars and Sufis. Each of them played an important role in the political and cultural life of Central Asia. This article is explicitly dedicated to the origins of the founder of the Ahrārī family - Khwāja Ahrār, his descendants, the competition for primacy between the internal branches, and the fate of some of their famous representatives.

Keywords: Şiddīqī family, Khwāja Ahrār, Central Asia, and waqf endowments.

Ahrārī family was established by Khwāja Nāşir al-Dīn ‘Ubayd-Allah Ahrār (d. 896/1490), a famous Sufi leader of the Naqshbandīya order. Khwājah Ahrār b. Khwāja Maḥmūd b. Shihāb al-Dīn was born in Tashkent. He was Şiddīqī from his patrilineal line but was connected to the Tirmīdh sayyids and ‘Umarī khwājas through his maternal grandfather (Khwāja Dāwūd) and to the ‘Alawī sayyids through his maternal grandmother (Khwāja Tāj al-Dīn Darghāmī) [1, 114; 6, 228.]. Thus, the theory of the origin of the Ahrārīs along different lines was successfully completed. However, the approach of presenting and legalizing their genealogy was generally different from the traditional three versions of the legitimization of other Şiddīqī khwājas of Central Asia [4, 207; 5, 7].

Khwāja Ahrār had great esteem among Timurids of Transoxiana and Khurasan. His descendants also had a significant influence at the courts of the Central Asian khanates, Mughal India, and the Chagataid Yārkan Khanate. However, we must not forget that the Ahrārīs had gone through a challenging period before this achievement. These difficulties are associated with the restoration of reputation with the new rulers of the region, as well as the return of lost property. But this process took place against the background of competition for spiritual leadership and property among the two inner branches of this dynasty. Here two branches of the Ahrārīs came into existence from the sons of Khwāja Ahrār: Khwāja Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah (d. 908/1502) and Khwāja Muḥammad Yaḥyā (d. 906/1500). The economic opportunity and political influence of Muḥammad Yaḥyā’s branch were higher because Khwāja Ahrār chose him as his financial and authoritative heir. Thus, Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah did not have rights to the crown when his younger brother was alive [2, 80-91]. Muḥammad Yaḥyā and his children were executed due to a decree by Shībānī-Khān in 906/1500. As a result, the property of the Ahrārīs was confiscated and this branch underwent a provisional crisis. The political accusations at that time did not allow Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah new attempts at progress.

Initially, the competition between the two Ahrārī branches on waqf property rights began to change in favor of the family of Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah. The beginning of this process was the departure of the Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥādī b. Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah (d. 938/1531-32) to his grandfather's grave after his uncle's death. The death of Shībānī-Khān and the warming relationships between the Shībānīd sultāns and the Ahrārīs intensified competition between the two branches. As a result, the representatives of the branches began to repatriate the confiscated property and take over the management of Khwāja Ahrār’s waqf endowments. One of them was a brother of Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥādī, Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥaq (d. 959/1551). Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥaq is also known as Mawlānā Shaykh and is the author of the book “Maqāmāt-i Khwāja Ahrār”. He succeeded in his claims against a person who had appropriated one of the lands from Khwāja Ahrār’s waqf endowments in Samarqand at the Shari’a court of Bukhara on 27 Dhul-qa’da 919 (27 November 1514). A year later, at the beginning of the month of Jumād al-ākhir 920 (23 July 1514) another Ahrārī, Khwāja Muḥammad Yaḥyā b. Muḥammad Bāqī b. Muḥammad Yaḥyā b. Khwāja Ahrār (hereafter Muḥammad Yaḥyā II), was able to get the Shari’a court of Tashkent to give Khwāja Ahrār’s waqf endowments to his small son, Khwājah Muḥammad Yaḥyā, with the testimony of the Shaykh al-Islām Khwāja ‘Abd al-Radhhdhāq al-Baqā and the other persons of authority as witnesses.

In fact, the sections of the waqf-nāmahs regarding who would become mutawallī after Khwājah Ahrār were amended many times. In the waqf-nāmah of 874/1470, Khwājah Ahrār claimed that his descendants should be mutawallī. In the waqf-nāmah of 894/1489, it was stated that the title of mutawallī would pass to Muḥammad Yaḥyā and his descendants. In two waqf-nāmahs before 894/1490 it was stated that his sons, Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah and Muḥammad Yaḥyā, would have equal rights to the position. The clashes between the two Ahrārī branches did not last long. In 8 Rajab 928 (3 June 1522), the Sharia court of Samarqand considered a case of Muḥammad Yaḥyā II against his

relative Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥafīd b. Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥaq claimed the right of mutawallī to the waqf garden in the village of Khwāja Kafshīr (*see*: Fig. A). As a result, the

right of mutawallī was bestowed to Muḥammad Yaḥyā’s descendants and the claims of Muḥammad Yaḥyā II were satisfied.

Khwāja ‘Ubayd-Allah Aḥrār

Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah
(d. 908/1502)

Muḥammad Yaḥyā I
(d. 906/1500)

Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥaq
(d. 959/1551)

Khwāja Muḥammad Bāqī
(d. 906/1500)

Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥafīd - Khwāja ṣadr

Khwāja Muḥammad
Yaḥyā II

Fig. A.

After that Muḥammad Yaḥyā II continued to regain the private and family waqfs of Khwāja Aḥrār and restore the rights of Muḥammad Yaḥyā’s I branch. In particular, he succeeded in a case that was heard in the Sharia court of Samarqand in 940/1533. He even succeeded in regaining property in the countryside of Samarqand which had been taken with the deed (*yārliq*) of the Shībānīd ‘Abd al-Laṭīf-Khān (r. 1540-52) and the remission of several taxes on 3 Shawwāl of 950 (30 December 1543). Muḥammad ‘Abd-Allah’s branch held control of the waqf properties in Kabul for a while. In particular, Khwāja Aḥrār’s waqf endowments in Kabul were controlled between 946-51/1540-45 by Khwāja ‘Abd al-Ḥaq, the spiritual mentor of the Bābūrīd Kāmran Mīrzā, and Khāwand Maḥmūd in 952/1546, along with a brief interference by Khumāyūn (r. 1530-39, 1555-56).

The victory of Muḥammad Yaḥyā II enabled his branch not only to control waqf properties in Mawāraunnahr, but also to regain his authority in the political arena. For the next three centuries, this branch of Aḥrārīs occupied the position of Shaykh al-Islām of Samarqand (with some breaks). For example, Hāshim-khwāja Aḥrārī had great influence in the 17th century during a period of political disturbance. Yūsuf-khwāja b. Ya’qūb-khwāja Aḥrārī was the son-in-law of Jānīd ruler Nādir Muḥammad-Khān (r. 1641-45). His son who was born of another marriage, Zakariyā-khwāja Aḥrārī (d. 1100/1688) in 1685s agreed to marry his daughter to the ruler of Khiva Anūsha-Khān (r. 1663-87). Another member of this branch Shihāb al-Dīn-khwāja Aḥrārī was appointed as Shaykh al-Islām of Samarqand in 1170/1756 by Muḥammad Raḥīm-Bī (r. 1747-59), who started the Manghit dynasty in Bukhara. During the 19th century, Sulṭān-khān khwājam Aḥrārī too occupied this position. In the Khanate of Khoqand, ruler of the Ming dynasty ‘Umar-Khān (r. 1810-22) in 1815 introduced the position *khwaja-kalan* (like *naqib*) and was appointed to this post Sulṭān-khān-tūra Aḥrārī – Adā. In the 19th century, shaykhs and mutawallīs of Khwāja Aḥrār’s shrine in Samarqand claimed to belong to Muḥammad Yaḥyā’s branch. In

particular, O. Sukhareva encountered representatives of this branch while studying the Aḥrārī khwājas in the Khwāja Kafshīr neighborhood [3, 157-168]. In the 19th century, the administrators of Khwāja Aḥrār’s waqf properties in Tashkent, ‘A’zam-khān-tūra Muminkhanov and Naṣr al-Dīn-khān-tūra Turakhanov, also regarded themselves as the descendants of Muḥammad Yaḥyā I.

Thus, after Khwāja Aḥrār, his sons did not use his authority for long. The new ruler of the region, Shībānī-Khān, and his first heirs, differing from the Timurids, chose other spiritual mentors for themselves. Only a quarter of a century later, the Aḥrārīs were able to restore their authority in the region. However, this began with internal competition for spiritual leadership and for mastering the legacy of Khwāja Aḥrār between the two branches of family. All these ended in favor of the descendants of Muḥammad Yaḥyā, who was the youngest son of Khwāja Aḥrār.

References

1. Muḥammad bin Burhānuddīn Samarqandī. *Silsilat-al-‘Arifīn wa Tadhkirat-al-Ṣidīqīn*. – Tehran, 2009. 452 p.
2. Kazakov B. *Synov’ia Khodji Akhrara i poslednye Timuridy // Dukhovenstvo i politicheskaja jizn’ na Blizhnem i Srednem Vostoke v period feodalizma*. – Moskva, 1985, pp. 80-91.
3. Sukhareva O.A. *Potomki Khodja Akhrara // Dukhovenstvo i politicheskaja jizn’ na Blizhnem i Srednem Vostoke v period feodalizma*. – Moskva, 1985, pp. 157-168.
4. Sulstonov U. *Three Versions of Siddiqi-Khwaja Family Legitimation in Central Asia // Central Asian Journal of Social Sciences and History*. 2021. Volume 2 (12), pp. 206-211.
5. Sulstonov U. *The Practice of Legalization and Documentation of Genealogy of Sainly Families in Central Asia // Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*. 2022. Volume 11 (Dec), pp. 7-10.
6. Fakhr al-Dīn ‘Alī Ṣafī. *Rashahāt ‘ayn al-hayāt*. – Tāshkand: Ghulamīya, 1329/1911. 394 p.